

BASIC PHYSICAL QUALITIES AND METHODS OF THEIR IMPROVEMENT IN WRESTLING

Khurshidbekov A.M.

Doctoral student of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14558039>

Abstract. *The importance of the sport of wrestling, the impact of popularization of this sport among young people on the development of society are described. The main attention is focused on issues of formation of physical qualities of wrestlers. The world standards of each physical quality are analyzed.*

Keywords: *wrestling, Endurance, Speed, Flexibility, national sport. exercise, health.*

In order to make young people morally perfect, physical education workers should pay more attention to mass physical culture and sports activities in cities and villages, develop various types of sports suitable for urban and rural youth, and regularly hold sports competitions in general education schools. It is necessary for our youth not only to be educated, but also to be spiritually beautiful, healthy, fit, and physically strong. These can be achieved due to the popularization of the sports movement, the development of physical education that covers all young people, the training of their willpower, and the physical preparation for work and defense. Sports training for athletes in wrestling is conducted in special sports schools. Our youth should be not only well-educated and spiritually beautiful, but also healthy and fit. Wrestling is one of the national sports, and it is important to strengthen the feelings of patriotism and national pride in the hearts of the growing young generation through this exercise, and to raise them to be physically healthy and mentally mature. Taking these aspects into account, attention is paid to all types of sports at the level of state policy in our country. In particular, on November 4, 2020, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the national sport of wrestling and further increase its international prestige" was adopted. It is aimed at developing the physical qualities of the wrestlers, developing the qualities of strength, quickness, willpower, endurance and flexibility. Strength is the ability to absorb external influences with muscle tension. In the development of muscle strength, muscle tissue increases in size and shape. By increasing the size of all muscle groups of the body, the body structure can be improved. Strength quality is important in wrestling. The force generated during movements is called dynamic force. The force generated by muscle tension without movement is called static force. The index of influence on weight with the help of muscle strength is called the absolute strength index. Relative strength is the ratio of absolute strength to body weight. For example, if a 50 kg weightlifter can lift a 100 kg stone, his absolute force is 100 F. Relative strength is equal to absolute strength divided by 100 F by body weight, i.e. 2.0 F. That's why in weightlifting competitions, even when the results shown by light weight athletes are equal to others, they are given the victory. The quality of strength can be developed using exercises with weights, on simulators, rubber expanders and exercises with the resistance of a partner. The quality of strength is considered necessary in wrestling and plays an important role in wrestling exercises, where exercises with heavy loads are performed. Power indicators are measured in dynamometers. Strength can be developed by lifting weights, performing exercises on special equipment and devices, and overcoming body resistance. The methods of developing strength consist of the ability to lift weights at the level of possibility and

the methods of performing exercises with high repetitions and light loads. The method of lifting weights at the level of possibility: exercises are explained by lifting heavy loads up to the limit of possibility. Exercises can be performed 1-3 times in one attempt. The number of attempts during training is 5-6 times, and it is recommended to rest up to 10 minutes after each attempt. In this method, muscle endurance is increased. Method of repetition of exercises: 5-15 repetitions of exercises with loads of moderate weight. During training, the number of attempts is 3-5 times, after each attempt you can rest for 3-5 minutes. In this method, effective increase in muscle size is observed. Method of training with light loads: recommends performing exercises with light and moderate weights. Exercises in this style are 15-25 times per attempt. Exercises should be done at speed. During one training, the number of attempts can be 5-6 times, the rest period between them can be 5-10 minutes. This form of training is the basis for the development of quick strength qualities of the participants. It is recommended to do strength training in the preparation and main part of the training. At this time, physical and mental fatigue will not occur in the body. In order to achieve effective results in the development of muscle strength, it is advisable to use exercises separately for muscle groups. In developing the qualities of strength, it is necessary to pay great attention to breathing processes. It is recommended to hold your breath when lifting heavy loads for a short time, not to take deep breaths during strength exercises, and to regulate breathing during strength exercises. Endurance is the ability to perform physical activities for a long time, overcoming external and internal influences. Endurance can also be understood as the ability to resist fatigue. To develop endurance, it is necessary to perform physical activities for a long time and learn to cope with fatigue. Long distance runs, cross country and marathon runs can be used to develop endurance in wrestlers. Endurance can be divided into two types. General endurance is the ability to perform activities at moderate intensity for a long time, and this activity is carried out at the expense of aerobic capacity. General endurance is explained by the effective functioning of the heart, blood vessels, breathing and other organs of the body during physical activities. Long-distance running, swimming and cycling exercises are used to develop general endurance. Common endurance training techniques include repetitive, consistent, sequential, interval, and alternating forms of exercise. Specific endurance can be called the ability to withstand fatigue, which is consistent with the form of professional activity or specialized sport. Forms of special endurance: quick endurance; strength endurance: static endurance. Acrobatics, gymnastics and jumping exercises, as well as special movements of wrestlers, are widely used to develop the agility of wrestlers. Speed is the ability to perform actions quickly. It can be understood as the ability of the body to respond quickly when performing actions. The reaction of movements is one of the main forms of demonstrating agility. Physiological processes such as creating an understanding of movement, assimilation of this information in the nervous system, and giving instructions to the muscle system to perform activities are carried out during the demonstration of speed. High-skilled athletes can spend 0.1-0.2 seconds in demonstrating speed. Hereditary characteristics have a great influence on the development of speed. Speed is the basis of sprinting, martial arts, boxing, fencing and many other sports. Speed is based on simple and complex reactions. A normal reaction is a rapid response to a known signal. The permission of the referees to start the game or actions, the processes of entering the actions after the whistle are carried out at the expense of a simple reaction.

Reaction to unfamiliar actions in a complex reaction. In these processes, the wrestlers are interpreted by performing actions in response to unexpected actions. Doing quick exercises and

doing them many times helps to develop simple reactions. Fighting competitions can be used to develop complex reactions. In the development of general quickness, it is advisable to use a lot of fast exercises, throwing and competition methods. In the demonstration of speed, demands are made to spend a short time to perform the movement, to quickly perform parts of the movement, and to increase the speed of repetition of movements. The ability to speed is in many cases innate and is improved during sports training. The quality of speed is also one of the leading qualities and has its importance in all types of fighting. Wrestlers develop the quality of quickness in the types of wrestling that require high-speed actions in a short period of time. In the development of speed, along with special quick movements of the fight, short distance runs and sprints are widely used. Flexibility is the ability to perform a wide range of movements. Flexibility is genetic, but flexibility is also influenced by age and gender, as well as physical fitness. General and special elasticity are distinguished. General flexibility is the ability to perform all movements in a wide range, which is explained by the mobility of the joints. Specific flexibility is the flexibility shown when performing sports-related movements. Flexibility is the leading physical quality in wrestling. Forms of flexibility: Active flexibility: performed using muscle power. - Slow elasticity: it is done under the influence of external influences. Dynamic flexibility: performed during movements. Static flexibility: the body position does not change. Flexibility depends on the flexibility of muscles, joints and ligaments. To increase flexibility, it is necessary to perform exercises to warm up the muscles, massage or stretch the group of flexor muscles. Flexibility is also affected by external temperature and time of day. Flexibility is also an innate ability that can be further developed during training. Nevertheless, the quality of flexibility, like the quality of quickness and agility, is considered a quality subject to rapid negative change and requires regular physical training and special exercises. According to age, these physical qualities are observed to decrease. In the development of flexibility, it is recommended to slowly perform exercises that provide stretching of muscles, tendons and joints. It is advisable to increase the speed and volume of exercises at the same time. Exercises can be performed from simple, flexible, stretching wide range of motion, with the help of external influences, with rubber expanders and weights. Regularly engaging in these forms of exercise, extensive use of physical loads that affect the elasticity of the joints, develops the flexibility of the joints. Physical qualities are manifested in the process of performing actions in accordance with the purpose of action.

Agility is the ability to perform tasks of physical movements quickly, accurately and efficiently. In the development of agility, tools and equipment related to professional activities or sports are used. Agility is manifested by the sensitivity of the muscles, the ability to control oneself, the development of the nervous center, the ability to quickly change movements and the ability to quickly adapt to the complexity of movements. Also, the ability to quickly learn new actions, to manage actions in accordance with rapidly changing conditions, also determines the qualities of agility. Agility can be seen as the ability to quickly master actions, to control actions, and to be able to quickly start new actions. In the development of agility, attention is paid to the development of the wrestler's ability to sense space and time and control movements. Agility is a unique quality that manifests itself in different ways in a fight. In the types of fighting for agility, muscle tension occurs simultaneously, muscle tension occurs based on space requirements, agility is performed in accordance with space (place) and time, all actions to demonstrate agility are mutually compatible. A high level of agility is the ability to maintain body balance in any movement. Movements specific to fighting methods can be widely used in the development of agility. The

following tasks are solved in the development of agility; Ability to control movements when performing complex exercises; Organization of actions in accordance with rapid changes in conditions; Accurate and quick performance of movement tasks. In the development of agility, the importance of complex physical exercises and movements in which types of struggle are performed and the shape changes quickly is of great importance. Exercises should be complex, non-traditional, offer a new approach to movement tasks, inventiveness and unexpected actions. It is necessary to develop agility in every training. Because it is necessary to constantly improve this ability, to enrich it with new movement skills and abilities, to form the ability to quickly adapt to conditions, to develop the ability to control one's actions in space and time, and to improve the speed and accuracy of actions in accordance with the types of combat. The development of the ability to control movements is carried out with the development of the ability to feel space and time, the speed, form and rhythm of movements, the position of the body and its parts in space. A high level of development of one of the physical qualities leads to the improvement of other qualities. In the processes of physical training, it is necessary to pay great attention to the harmonious development of physical qualities. As the level of physical training increases, wrestlers try to improve a special quality. In many cases, such training can lead to disproportionate development of physical qualities. Static exercises performed with a heavy load can prevent the acquisition of fast movements. To develop speed, it is not advisable to carry out heavy loads. Examples of this include weightlifters having difficulty performing sports movements or sprinters having difficulty lifting heavy loads. Therefore, when organizing the physical training of athletes, it is necessary to pay attention to the mutual development of physical qualities. For this, one day should be allocated to the weekly routine of sports games, swimming, wrestling, gymnastics and acrobatics, as well as strength training. While developing wrestlers' physical qualities, special attention should be paid to education of special qualities.

REFERENCES

1. K. Yusupov. Techniques and tactics of the international rules of wrestling. Tashkent 2005.
2. Tashkent., State Institute of Physical Culture of Uzbekistan, 2005 - 171 p
3. N.Kh. Azizov. Turkestan wrestling with a belt. Tashkent: Teacher 1998.
4. Yusupov K., Kurash, T., 1999; Mominov A., President. Sports. Victory!, T., 2001.
5. Goncharova O.V. Development of physical abilities of young athletes. Tashkent. 2017